

NEW LOW DIELECTRIC CONSTANT MATERIAL FROM CHICKEN FEATHERS AND SOYBEANS

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SUMMARY: The continuing demand for higher speed electronic devices has driven an extensive search for new low dielectric constant (k) materials that can replace silicon dioxide as the insulator, and polymers such as epoxy and polyimide used in the circuit boards. In a typical microchip, performance gain is mostly limited by the intra- and interlayer capacitance, dictated primarily by the dielectric constant of the insulators, known as dielectrics. We have developed a new low- k material from renewable resources, using chicken feathers (CF) and soybean oils. This offers economic incentives through the use of cheaper materials, but also environmental advantages through the use of abundant renewable materials, which promote global sustainability. The k values of the new composite materials developed from chicken feather fibers and soybean resin decrease from 2.7 to 1.7 at 25°C, with an increase of chicken feather fiber content. The new CF dielectric material has a lower dielectric constant than conventional semiconductor insulators such as silicon dioxide ($k = 3.8-4.2$), epoxies ($k = 4.1$), polyimides and other dielectric materials. Also, the new dielectric is lightweight and rigid. The density of the composite material decreases with an increase of chicken feather fiber content and can be made to be less than 1 g/cm³ at a CF volume fraction of about 30%. The incorporation of CF fiber in the soybean resin results in a considerable increase of stiffness and strength of the soybean oil-based composites. In order to check lithographic process potential, we printed a multi-chip module (MCM) and an Optical Element on a chicken feather dielectric by using a semiconductor fabrication technique. Our results suggest that the new dielectric material from renewable resources is a promising alternative in a variety of electronic applications such as high-speed circuits, high performance capacitor, electrical cable insulation, electronic packaging and components. The new composite material is an affordable, bio-based, environmentally friendly and natural material.

KEYWORDS: low dielectric constant, renewable resources, chicken feather fiber, soybean oil, and lightweight composite

INTRODUCTION

The continuing demand for higher speed electronic devices has driven an extensive search for new low dielectric constant (k) materials that can replace silicon dioxide as the insulator, and polymers such as epoxy and polyimide used in the circuit boards. In a typical microchip, performance gain is mostly limited by the intra- and interlayer capacitance, dictated primarily by the dielectric constant of the insulators, known as dielectrics [1]. A decrease of the dielectric constant of the insulator containing the printed circuits, increases the operating speed, minimizes the “cross-talk” effects between metal interconnects, and diminishes the power consumption [2]. Development of low- k dielectric materials is considered to be one of the main issues in modern high-speed microelectronics.

Developing a low- k material from renewable resources, such as hollow keratin fibers from avian (chicken, turkey, goose, etc) feathers and plant oil from soybean, is quite attractive from economic and environmental perspectives. They offer economic incentives through the use

of cheaper materials, but also environmental advantages through the use of abundant renewable materials, which promote global sustainability. The new low- k material is a natural, bio-based and environmentally friendly material. The hollow feather fiber, composed of the protein keratin with an alpha-helical structure at the molecular level, is highly microcrystalline and is tough enough to withstand both mechanical and thermal stress [3]. The use of the avian feather fibers as reinforcing fibers in composite materials offers an environmentally benign solution for feather disposal. Due to the hollow structure of the keratin fibers, a given volume of the fiber innately contains a significant volume of air. Air is an ideal dielectric material, representing the minimum dielectric constant of 1.0.

Soybean oil-based resin is a low polarity, hydrophobic material based on triglycerides, which is the major component of plant and animal oils. Triglycerides are composed of three fatty acids joined at a glycerol juncture [4]. The Affordable Composites from Renewable Sources (ACRES) Program at the University of Delaware has developed a broad range of chemical routes to utilize natural oils as a basis for polymers and composite materials [5-9]. The triglyceride-based materials display the necessary rigidity and strength required for structural applications.

In this study, we have developed a new low- k material suited to electronic applications using hollow keratin fibers and chemically modified soybean oil. A low-polarity soybean resin is used as the composite matrix and hollow microcrystalline keratin fibers are used as reinforcing fibers for taking advantage of the low- k of air. It was important that the resin did not displace the air by filling the hollow fibers. The essential properties for electronic applications, such as dielectric and mechanical properties, and the thermal expansion coefficients, of the new composites are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sample Preparation

Chemically modified soybean oils such as acrylated epoxidized soybean oils (AESO, Ebecryl 860, UCB Chemical Company) was mixed with 33wt% of reactive diluents of styrene monomer as a resin. During mixing, 3.0 wt% of cumyl hydroperoxide (Trigonox 239A, Akzo Chemicals) is added as an initiator, and 0.8 wt % of cobalt naphthenate with 6% metal content (CoNap, Witco) was added as an accelerator. Various concentrations of hollow keratin fibers (HF) from chicken feathers or the HF mats (supplied by Tyson Foods, Inc.) were physically mixed with the resin, or by resin infusion on the fiber mats, using a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process. The copolymerization reaction of the resin was carried out by redox decomposition of the free radical initiators using a metal promoter at room temperature to produce rigid composites. After room temperature curing, the samples were post-cured at 120°C for two hours.

Characterization

The HF fiber was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JEOL JXA-840). The sample was coated with gold using a sputter coater (Denton Vacuum Inc.).

The dielectric properties of the materials were measured on Dielectric Analyzer (DEA 2970, TA Instruments) with a heating rate of 2°C/min at a frequency of 100Hz. The dimension of a sample was 0.7 mm x 25.4 mm x 25.4 mm. In dielectric analysis, each sample was placed between two gold electrodes (parallel plate sensors, TA instruments).

The storage modulus of the new low- k material was measured using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA 2988, TA instruments) according to ASTM D5023. Fracture toughness was also measured to study the effect of HF content on the mechanical properties of the composites. The fracture toughness test was performed according to ASTM D5045 (three point bending mode) at room temperature. The crosshead speed of a tester (Instron 4201) was 1.27 mm/min.

The coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE), in-plane direction, were measured using a Thermo-mechanical Analyzer (TMA 2940, TA instruments) under a force of 0.05N at a heating rate of 5°C/min. The CTE is defined as the fractional change in length per unit change in temperature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The keratin fibers are light and hollow with an average diameter of 6 μm and a length of 8 mm, as shown in Figure 1. The nodes and hooks on the keratin fibers can improve the structural properties and increase surface area in the composite. The density of HF is about 0.80 g/cm^3 , and that of soybean resin about 1.08 g/cm^3 . The density of the new dielectric materials decreases with an increase of HF content and can be made to be less than 1 g/cm^3 at a HF volume fraction of about 30%. This contrasts with a density of typical epoxy-fiberglass circuit boards. The low density of the HF composites makes them suited to automotive and aeronautical applications in addition to electronic materials.

Figure 2 shows the k values of the new composite materials developed from hollow keratin fibers (HF) and soy oil resin, at a temperature of 25°C. The k values decrease from 2.7 to 1.7, with an increase of HF content approximately as,

$$k = k(\text{resin}) - \text{HF}$$

where HF is in the wt fraction of fiber. The new HF composite material has a lower dielectric constant than conventional semiconductor insulators such as silicon dioxide ($k = 3.8\text{-}4.2$ [2]), epoxies, polyimides and other dielectric materials. In integrated circuits (ICs), a decrease of the k value of the insulator increases the operating speed. The delay time of the electronic signal is proportional to the square root of k and values close to $k=1$ are most desirable. The measured k value of the HF mat itself was 1.7 because HF fibers contain a significant volume of air. The ideal minimum k value is 1.0, as represented by air and therefore, a porous or high-air content material may have dielectric constants in the ultra-low- k (<2.2) region [1]. The dielectric constant of Teflon film is about 1.9 [2]. However, they are too soft and thermally unstable at high temperature. There are also serious concerns about the effect of fluorinated dielectrics on the interconnect metals and metal liners at elevated temperatures [1]. Thermosetting epoxy resin has a k -value of 4.1 and is used for electromagnetic component (EMC), printed circuit board (PCB) and the resin-encapsulating type semiconductor devices [10]. The k value of soybean resin itself is 2.7 and the molding process of soybean resin can follow the lead of conventional unsaturated polyester or vinyl ester resins. The low viscosity resins are also capable of being spun into nano-size thin films. Thus, soybean resin alone can also be a substitute for petroleum-based resins in many electronic material applications.

The temperature dependence of the dielectric constant of HF composites is shown in Figure 3. The dielectric constant of the composite slightly increased with increasing temperature, resulting from the alignment of the dipoles when the composite softened with temperature. However, since the effect of temperature on the k -value of air is minimal, we expect relatively little change as noted for the pure HF mat in Figure 3.

In dielectric tests, the measured value is separated into dielectric constant (Permittivity, ϵ') and loss factor (ϵ''). The dependence of the loss factor upon HF content is given in Figure 4. Loss factor represents the energy required to align dipoles and move ions. The loss factor decreases with increasing HF content.

With the low- k values, the mechanical strengths are also essential properties for the material to be used in electronic applications. The incorporation of HF in the soy oil resin results in a considerable increase of stiffness and strength of the soybean oil-based composites. The storage modulus of soybean resin at 20°C is 1.87GPa. With the addition of 30wt% of the hollow keratin fibers, the storage modulus increased to 2.55GPa. Also, the fracture toughness K_{IC} of the HF composite material was determined to be 0.86 to 0.97MPa $\text{m}^{1/2}$, which is higher than silica-base dielectric materials [11]. In addition to their low density, the mechanical properties of the

Table 1. The CTE values of HF Composites

HF content, wt%	α below T _g , $\mu\text{m}/\text{m } ^\circ\text{C}$	α above T _g , $\mu\text{m}/\text{m } ^\circ\text{C}$
0	127.2	205.8
5	106.1	200.6
10	100.4	196.3
20	93.1	193.2
30	67.4	69.6

composites are significantly enhanced by the addition of the keratin fibers, suitable for electronic applications.

The coefficients of thermal expansion (CTE) of the HF composites are shown in Table 1. The CTE decreased with increasing HF content and these values are quite low, especially for the 30wt% sample. In this case, the 30wt% sample is a VARTM processed sample using HF mats and the hollow fibers have high in-plane orientation. The CTE of the 30wt% composite below the glass transition temperature, 67.4 ppm/ $^\circ\text{C}$, is low enough for electronic applications, and similar to the value of silicon material (66 ppm/ $^\circ\text{C}$) [11] or polyimides (~ 59 ppm/ $^\circ\text{C}$) [12]. However, the CTE of the AESO is higher and changes abruptly above its glass transition temperature (T_g). The glass transition temperature of AESO resin cured at room temperature was about 70 $^\circ\text{C}$ and can be increased by chemical modification [6]. From an atomic perspective, the CTE reflects an increase in the average distance between atoms with increasing temperature [13]. The thermal expansion of AESO resin is compensated with the thermal contraction of HF fibers in the longitudinal (oriented) direction. Interactions between resin and HF fibers also act to resist changes in dimension with increasing temperature. The CTE can be further decreased by increasing the glass transition temperature and cross-linking density of the network structure, resulting in increasing chain stiffness.

In order to check the lithographic process potential, we printed a multi-chip module (MCM) and an Optical Element on the new HF dielectric materials by using a semiconductor fabrication technique (Figure 3) in the Nano-Optics Fabrication facility (courtesy of Dr Dennis Prather) at the University of Delaware. Incorporating low-*k* materials into viable sub micron fabrication schemes will necessitate the use of chemical mechanical polishing processes to meet the critical dimension requirements of current ICs. Although detailed tests of the chip performance have not yet been carried out, our results suggest that the new dielectric material from renewable resources is a promising alternative in a variety of electronic applications such as high-speed circuits, high performance capacitor, electrical cable insulation, electronic packaging and components.

CONCLUSIONS

A new low-*k* material was developed from renewable resources using hollow keratin fibers (HF) and chemically modified soybean oil in this study. The new low-*k* material was a natural, bio-based and environmentally friendly material. The *k* value was found to be in the range of 1.7 to 2.7, depending on the HF fraction. The *k*-values were lower than that of a conventional semiconductor insulator material such as silicon dioxide, epoxies, polyimides and other dielectric materials. Also, the HF dielectric composite was lightweight and rigid, with good fracture toughness properties and approximates the shape and feel of a silicon dioxide insulator.

The coefficient of thermal expansion of new low- k material (67.4 ppm/ $^{\circ}$ C) was low enough for electronic applications, and similar to the value of silicon material or polyimides. Multi-Chip-Module circuit printing results suggest that the low-cost composite made with HF and plant oil has the potential to replace the dielectrics in microchips and circuit boards in the ever-growing electronic materials field.

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Figure 1. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrographs of chicken feathers. (a) Chicken feather fibers. (b) A small feather quill.

Figure 2. The dielectric constants of the HF composites at a temperature of 25°C as a function of HF content.

Figure 3. The dependency of the dielectric constants on temperature.

Figure 4. The loss factors of HF composites at a temperature of 25°C as a function of HF content.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. Pictures of the first chicken feather microchips printed by using a semiconductor fabrication technique. (a) Optoelectronic multi-chip module. (b) Diffractive optical element.